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Annotation. *The article is devoted to the life and work of Ivan Sergeevich Turgenev, an outstanding Russian writer of the 19th century, a master of psychological prose and realistic art. The work analyzes the main stages of his life, key works, as well as the influence of his work on the development of Russian literature.*

Key words: *serfdom, versification, humane ideas, inspiration, humanistic.*

He was an outstanding master of Russian prose, a writer of novels, stories, plays, short stories, essays and critical works. His literary legacy had a huge impact on the spiritual development of Russian society and left a noticeable mark on the history of Russian literature, decorating domestic and world culture. A negative attitude towards serfdom, sincere empathy with the needs of the people and progressive humanistic ideas served as his inspiration. Saltykov-Shchedrin in his obituary dedicated to this writer noted: "Turgenev's literary activity played a key role in our society along with the work of Nekrasov, Belinsky and Dobrolyubov." You have probably already guessed which writer we will dedicate our article to. Turgenev's creative biography began in 1834, during his years of study at the institute. The young writer's first experience was poetry. The author's debut work was the poem "Steno". After it was ready, Turgenev showed the result to his teacher, critic Pyotr Alexandrovich Pletnev. After a positive assessment of his work, Ivan Sergeyevich continued his work in the field of versification. Soon new works came out from under the pen of the young author: "To the Venus of Medici" and "Evening". In 1836, Turgenev tried his hand at criticism, published a review. By the age of 37, the young man had managed to prepare more than a hundred poems and several unfinished stories. He had an amazing capacity for work and worked tirelessly.¹

Throughout his creative path, Turgenev was deeply receptive to all new aspects of the life of Russian society. He had the ability to observe and resolve all current living and relevant events of our time, and his works were focused on posing the most pressing issues of Russian society that worried public discourse. The vivid chronicle of the Russian social movement of the last century was truthfully depicted in the works of artists, realists. The author's swan song is considered to be his cycle "Poems in Prose", the end of his entire creative path. He began to create this cycle in 1877. Turgenev

¹ <https://biograph.online>. Ivan Sergeevich Turgenev

initially began as a poet, but later moved on to writing prose. Turgenev was able to feel and embody in his work the unconventional ideas formulated by Chekhov in another literary era - at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries.²

The novelist was an honored guest at friendly gatherings. His was a place of pilgrimage.

The poet, author of essays, short stories, novels, stories, and articles created a work in which Turgenev the poet and Turgenev the prose writer met.

Turgenev's psychological method is as follows: "The psychologist must disappear in the artist, just as a skeleton disappears from view under a living and warm body, to which it serves as a strong but invisible support."

As a psychologist, he understood the human psyche and penetrated deeply into the inner world of his heroes. Turgenev's psychologism is of a subject-summary nature. Turgenev continued the Pushkin tradition of Russian literature.

In the late 1870s, Turgenev settled in France. Every spring, Turgenev met with Russia: greetings to the youth, speeches and dinners.

"Poems in Prose" is a chain of philosophical miniatures reflecting the main questions of existence: birth, friendship, love, hate, beauty, immortality, death. "Poems in Prose" at different times became the object of interest of researchers. One of the first to address the problem of the ideological and artistic originality of "Poems in Prose" was I. F. Annensky. The motives of old age, death, and the helplessness of man in the face of nature determine the worldview of the late Turgenev in the cycle of "Poems in Prose". On the one hand, the writer tried to understand and accept the finiteness and, in many ways, the insignificance of human life, perceived man as a toy in the hands of fate, and recognized the primacy of chance; on the other hand, he could not reconcile himself with the inevitable finiteness of human existence.³

Turgenev's miniatures expressively displayed such characteristic features as lyricism and diary-like nature.

The searches, reflections and contradictions of the last years of I.S. Turgenev's life are reflected in his "Poems in Prose", which is considered Turgenev's creative culmination. "Poems in Prose" call to look closely at the destinies of people, to think about your life, to comprehend it, to direct it to a high goal, a person. He lived only 64 years, but left behind many books. In his famous "Sketches of a Hunter" he gave us an idea of the magnificence of the Russian landscape - fields, forest edges and meadows, and also demonstrated the profound possibilities and appeal of the Russian language, which had reached previously unseen levels of beauty and poetry. The images of

² <https://www.dissercat.com>. Zakharchenko N.A. Lyrical beginning in the works of I.S. Turgenev of the 40-50s of the XIX century.

³ Gulevich Elena Vitalievna Ideological and artistic originality of the cycle "poems in prose" by I. S. Turgenev // Archivarius. 2016. No. 2 (6). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ideyno-hudozhestvennoe-svoeobrazie-tsikla-stihotvoreniya-v-proze-is-turgeneva> (date of access: 11/14/2024).

Russian girls he created, which began to be called by the writer's name - "Turgenev girls", have long since become historical and cultural types. His novels immerse us in eternal social and philosophical questions about choosing one's place in life, the fate of Russia, the tragedy of human existence in the face of the inexorable laws of life.⁴ Poems in prose appear in Turgenev's early works, in the form of lyrical and philosophical "inclusions" in the text, as a rule, in the description⁵ landscapes that make the reader think about the transience of human existence, death, loneliness, love, happiness, truth and much more⁶. Turgenev, as is known, remained a supporter of Peter's reforms until the end of his life, deeply honored the personality of the outstanding reformer, believing that the path he chose was the only possible one for Russia. All his life he remained faithful to the ideas of V. G. Belinsky, who blessed him in his writing career, and bequeathed to be buried next to him. This will of his was fulfilled⁷. We would like to conclude our article with a speech by Ernest Renan, a member of the French Academy, the author of *The Life of Jesus* and *The History of the Origin of Christianity*: *"...Turgenev was not only a famous writer: he was also a great man. His soul was not the soul of an individual, more or less richly gifted by nature, but was, in a sense, the conscience of an entire people. No man has ever embodied in himself so fully an entire nationality. The silent genius of the collective masses is the source of everything great. But the mind of the masses has no voice. It needs an exponent, a prophet who would speak for it. Honor and glory to the great Slavic race, whose appearance on the stage of history is the most striking phenomenon of our century. Happy is that nationality which, at the outset of its conscious life, could be represented in such images, at once naive and profound, real and mystical. When the future will show us the measure of what this amazing Slavic genius will give us, with his ardent faith, with his deep intuition, with his special views on life and death, with his need for martyrdom, with his thirst for the ideal - then Turgenev's paintings will be priceless documents, something like a portrait of a genius in childhood. Turgenev realized the difficulty of this role - the spokesman for one of the great families of humanity. He felt that he was responsible for many souls, and, as an honest man, he weighed his every word ... Brothers enemies, divided by such a different understanding of the ideal, come all to his grave! You all have the right to love him, for he belonged to everyone, he contained all of you in his heart!"*⁸

⁴ <https://arzbiblio.ru>. The first poet of Russian prose

⁶ <https://cheloveknauka.com>. Trofimova T. B. Literary and philosophical reminiscences and auto-reminiscences in the cycle "Poems in Prose" by I. S. Turgenev. Diss., St. Petersburg - 2004, p. 4

⁷ Generalov N.P. I.S.Turgenev: Russia and Europe. From the history of Russian-European literary and social relations. – SPb.: RHGI, 2003. – P.14

⁸ <http://lib2.pushkinskiydom.ru>. Generalov N.P. I.S.Turgenev: Russia and Europe. From the history of Russian-European literary and social relations. – SPb.: RHGI, 2003. – P.40

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